

The Influence of Media Powtoon on the Ability of Writing Procedure Texts for VII Class Students of Junior High School 3 Pakkat

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to determine the effect of Powtoon media on the ability to write procedural texts for class VII students of SMP Negeri 3 Pakkat, Academic Year 2020/2021. The population in this study amounted to 62 people, and the sample of this study amounted to 32 students who were taken by a simple random sampling process. The research method used in this research is the experimental method. Hypothesis testing using the "t" test. From the data processing, the average pretest = 63.81, standard deviation = 9.38, standard error = 1.68. In the posttest, the mean = 83.62, standard deviation = 5.08, standard error = 0.91. Based on the normality test, the results of the pretest and posttest were normally distributed. For the homogeneity test, the F value is obtained from the table with the real rate = 0.05 or $F_{count} < F_{table}$ or $3.40 < 4.17$. This proves that the sample states that the variance of the two variables is homogeneous. The results of the "t" test obtained a value of $t_o = 11.72$. After t_o is known, then the value will be consulted with table 1 at a significant level of 5% of 2.03. Based on the calculations that have been done, it can be seen that $t_o > t_{table}$ is $11.72 > 2.03$. Thus, H_o (nil hypothesis) is rejected, and H_a (alternative hypothesis) is accepted. This proves that there is an influence of Powtoon media on the ability to write procedural texts for Class VII students of SMP Negeri 3 Pakkat, Academic Year 2020/2021.

KEYWORDS: Powtoon Media, Writing Procedure Text

INTRODUCTION

In essence, language learning or teaching language skills aims to grow and develop students' language skills. Skilled in language means skilled in listening, skilled in speaking, skilled in reading, and skilled in writing in good and correct Indonesian.

In the teaching and learning process, especially during the current Covid-19 pandemic, a teacher needs the media as a tool in delivering material so that the learning delivered does not feel bored or boring because there are variations in the delivery.

In the entire learning process of students at school, writing activities are one of the activities that cannot be separated. During the learning process at school, students are often taught or even given assignments to write. In this case, writing means an activity in expressing ideas, ideas, thoughts, and insights into writing that is systematic and can be understood by others.

Researchers chose writing skills based on the reality they faced when implementing PPL (Field Experience Program) in September-December 2020 at SMP Negeri 3 Pakkat. Researchers observed the learning of students both online and offline and still seemed to be Many students are not able to write well. In this case, students seem to have difficulty in expressing their ideas and ideas through writing. However, according to the author, this is a natural thing because writing skills will not come naturally but through a teaching and learning process as well as practice.

In everyday life, writing skills have a very important role. Writing is an activity that cannot be avoided by all students, because all learning will certainly require students to be able to write well and correctly. In this case, it is necessary to have an appropriate and well-planned writing learning plan with effective learning strategies, so that students understand the understanding of writing skills, one of which is by writing procedural texts.

Learning about writing procedural texts is found in Indonesian class VII semester one lessons. The basic competence in this study is to present data on a series of activities in the form of procedural texts (about how to play regional musical instruments,

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regional dances, how to make souvenirs, etc.) by paying attention to structure, linguistic elements, and oral and written content. Procedure text learning is taught in class VIII in the second semester of the implementation of the 2013 curriculum. However, after undergoing a revision in 2017, procedural text learning is no longer taught in class VIII, but is taught in class VII in semester one. Procedure text is a text that contains a series of steps or actions to do something. In understanding procedural texts, students are required to understand in advance what things are to be prepared before doing the work. Researchers consider that this procedure text is a useful text for students, because through the procedure text they know how the steps in carrying out an activity or activity properly and correctly. Through procedural text learning, students know what to do before carrying out something they want to do.

Based on the facts and data obtained from initial observations, it is shown that research on writing procedure texts has never been done at SMP Negeri 3 Pakkat. Therefore, research on writing procedural texts is very important to study as there is still a lack of research on the ability of students to write procedural texts. Because the biggest obstacle for students in learning Indonesian is in the writing aspect, so that it inspires the author in conducting this research.

Based on this, it can be seen that educational institutions have used technology media as a means of education to improve the quality of education for educational institutions. A good planning is needed in an effective learning. Likewise, the media to be used must require good planning. Teachers must be able to work with integrated learning components, including the media used in learning.

Audio visual media is one of the educational media that can be used in learning to write. Audio-visual media is a tool in learning related to the senses of sight and hearing. Powtoon is one example of audio-visual media used by researchers in conducting this research.

The learning model with powtoon media is a learning approach that can provide entertainment for students to quickly absorb material according to their abilities and interests in completing their tasks. The problems presented are adjusted to the expected response and with sufficient time allocation, so that students have time to understand the material and evaluate their potential in a fresh and entertained brain state.

Powtoon learning media is an online service to create a presentation that has a variety of very interesting animation features such as cartoon animation, handwritten animation, as well as livelier transition effects and very easy timing. So that the learning process is not boring and not monotonous, the teacher makes various efforts with the learning process in various ways. This is done so that the material presented by a teacher in the learning process can be understood by every student. No exception using the media in schools or where teachers teach. Some use the media Charta (diagrammatic presentation of a visual), OHP (a tool for

Formulation of the problem

1. Based on the background, identification, and problem boundaries, the formulation of the problem in this study is as follows:
2. How is the influence of Powtoon media in learning procedure text writing for class VII students of SMP Negeri 3 Pakkat?
3. How is the influence of Powtoon media in improving learning outcomes in Indonesian language learning?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Learning Media

Learning media is a component of a delivery strategy that can contain messages that will be conveyed to students in the form of tools, people, and materials. Media is also defined as a learning tool that can be used to facilitate learning activities. Based on this understanding, the media in brief is an intermediary between the sender of information and the recipient of information.

Learning media can be understood as "everything that can convey and distribute messages from sources in a planned manner so as to create a conducive learning environment where the recipient can carry out the learning process efficiently and effectively". Based on this understanding, learning media is any tool used to increase the effectiveness of the types of teaching and learning activities so that learning is more interesting and students can capture information easily. Media has an important role in the learning process, namely helping communication between a teacher and students. Media (plural of the word medium), is a word that comes from the Latin *medius*, which literally means "middle", "intermediary" or "introduction". Therefore, the media can be interpreted as an intermediary or an introductory message from the sender to the recipient of the message.

Media can be in the form of materials (software) and tools (hardware). Meanwhile, according to Gerlach and Ely, that the media if understood in broad outline are human, material, or events that build conditions, which cause students to be able to acquire knowledge, skills, or attitudes.

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Several definitions of media are explained by several experts. Media according to the American National Education Association is media within the scope of education as one of the objects that can be manipulated, seen and heard, read, or discussed, along with the instruments used for certain activities.

Comotions on instructional technology, media was born as a result of the communication revolution that can be used for learning purposes in addition to teachers, textbooks and whiteboards. According to Gagne, media are various types of components in the student environment that can stimulate students to learn. According to Briggs, learning media is a means to provide incentives for learning so that the learning process occurs.

In communication studies, the term media is often attached to the word mass, mass media, whose manifestation can be seen in the form of newspapers, magazines, radio, video, television, computers, internet, and so on.

The term learning can be understood through two words, namely construction and instruction. Construction is carried out for students (in the case of passive students), while instruction is carried out by students (here, active students). Therefore, learning can be understood as everything that is done with a view to facilitating learning.

Powtoon Media

Powtoon learning media is one of the audio and visual-based learning media. According to Mafita Sari & Suci Rohayati (2017:1) "Powtoon is one type of online service that has interesting animation features in delivering messages in the form of videos. This is one alternative from developing technology to use interactive learning media on material that is considered difficult to be more fun because it is presented with a combination of several media such as audio and visual. Therefore, this media is very interesting to use in the classroom as an alternative learning media so that students do not get bored with learning but also make teacher learning media more varied.

Powtoon itself is the name of an IT-based application that is useful for making animated cartoon videos concisely and free of charge. This media is expected to make students more receptive to the material because the material looks more interesting. The advantages of Powtoon media are the various animation features and more evocative transition effects.

Audio Visual Media

Audio visual media is a visual media that combines the use of sound and requires additional work to produce it. Audio visual media is a form of learning media that is easy and affordable.

Audio-visual media is a type of media that focuses the attention of learning on the senses of hearing and sight. This is confirmed by Yudhi Munadi's opinion in his book on audio-visual media. According to him, audio-visual media is a medium that involves two senses at once in one process, namely the sense of sight and the sense of hearing. Based on these two understandings, it can be said that audio-visual media is a combination of two media, namely audio media and visual media at the same time.

Audio-visual media are various kinds of media that contain sounds that can be heard and contain images that can be seen. The application of audio-visual media in learning is considered very optimal because it can increase motivation and interest in learning and can clarify the material presented. At the beginning of the learning process, the media must be shown something that can attract the attention of all students.

Audio-visual media is very well used in every learning process, especially in Indonesian writing materials. The use of this media makes students more creative and motivated in producing a written work through a form of essay. This motivation will clearly affect student learning outcomes. Learning using audio-visual media is very appropriate to use in learning to write procedure texts. This is because audio-visual media in the form of video presents elements of sound and images, thus helping students and generating motivation in writing procedural texts.

The Nature of Writing

Writing is a means of developing thinking or reasoning by collecting facts, connecting them and then drawing conclusions. Widyamartaya argues that writing can be understood as a whole series of activities a person expresses ideas and conveys through written language to the reader to be understood exactly as intended by the author. Cheapimin believes that writing can also be interpreted as an effort to communicate which has its own rules and habits.

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RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A. Location and Time of Research

This research was conducted at SMP Negeri 3 Pakkat, which is located on Jl. Raja Simtor, Sipagabu Village, Pakkat District, Humbang Hasundutan Regency. This research was conducted in the even semester, 2020/2021 Academic Year.

B. Research Method

The research method is basically a scientific way to obtain data with a specific purpose and use. Not only general understanding, there are also research methods according to several experts as follows:

1. Muhammad Nasir. The research method is important for a researcher to achieve a goal, and can find answers to the problems posed.
2. Heri Rahyubi. The research method is a model that can be used with teaching and learning activities to achieve a process in the learning well.
3. Prof. M.E Winarno. The research method is to carry out a series of systematic and thorough scientific activities.
4. Muhiddin Sirat. The research method is the step used to select a case and determine the title of the research.

Research design

The design in this study is a one group Pre-Test-post Test Design. This design was used because this study only involved one class, namely the experimental class which began with pretest before being given treatment and then posttest after being given treatment.

In this design, measurements are performed twice. With this design, the effect of the experiment can be ascertained because it has used a preliminary test. Before starting the treatment, the class was given a pre-test or pre-test to measure the initial conditions. In this case, the researcher used a procedure text writing test for students twice, namely a test before using powtoon media, and a test after using powtoon media.

The design model is as follows:

Table 1. Experimental design of One Group Pre-Test and Post-Test Design Information :

class	<i>Pre-Test</i>	<i>Perlakuan</i>	<i>Post-Test</i>
Experiment	T ₁	X	T ₂

T1 = first measurement before using powtoon media (pretest). X = treatment or application of powtoon media

T2 = the second measurement after using powtoon media (posttest).

C. Population and Research Sample

According to Sugiyono, (2011: 80) population is a generalization area consisting of objects or subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics determined by researchers to be studied and then drawn conclusions.

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Based on the above opinion, the population in this study were all seventh grade students of SMP Negeri 3 Pakkat for the 2020/2021 academic year, as many as 62 students divided into 2 classes as shown in the table below:

Table 2. Population of Class VII students of SMPN 3 Pakkat T/A 2020/2021

No.	Class students	Man	Woman	Amount
	VII A	15	17	32
	VII B	12	18	30
Total				62

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According to Sugiyono, (2011: 81) the sample is part of the number and characteristics possessed by the population. In this study, the population has been divided into several sections based on the existing classes, namely class VII A, and class VII B.

There are several ways of sampling and one of them is by random sampling. Sugiyono, (2010:132) states, "Because the sampling technique is random, then everyone has the same opportunity to be selected as a sample." In this case, the random person is not the person but the class, which is between class VII A and class VII B.

RESULTS

Data Analysis Ability to Write Procedure Text Before Using Powtoon Media

The data that will be presented below are data obtained from the pre-test given to students. The description of the data can be seen in the following data distribution table.

Table 3. Distribution of Pre-test Frequency

X	F	FX	$x - \bar{x}$	$(x - \bar{x})^2$	FX^2
45	2	90	-18,81	353,81	707,62
52	6	312	-11,81	139,47	836,82
63	10	630	-0,81	0,65	6,5
68	4	272	4,19	17,55	70,2
69	3	207	5,19	26,93	80,79
73	2	146	9,19	84,45	168,9
75	4	300	11,19	125,21	500,84
85	1	85	21,19	449,01	449,01
Σ	32	2042			2820,68

Data Analysis Ability to Write Procedure Text after Using Powtoon Media

The data presented below are the data obtained from the posttest given to students. The description of the data can be seen in the following frequency distribution table:

Table 4. Distribution of Post-test Frequency

X	F	FX	$x - \bar{x}$	$(x - \bar{x})^2$	FX^2
74	2	148	-9,62	92,54	185,08
78	2	156	-5,62	31,58	63,16
80	8	640	-3,62	13,10	104,80
82	2	164	-1,62	2,62	5,24
84	8	672	0,38	0,14	1,12

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86	4	344	2,38	5,66	22,64
90	3	270	6,38	40,70	122,10
94	3	282	10,38	107,74	323,22
∑	32	2676			827,36

DISCUSSION

After conducting such a long research procedure, for example by analyzing the data, then testing the data hypotheses, the researcher finally got a result that was not in vain. Learning to write procedural texts using Powtoon media has a positive effect on the ability to write procedural texts. Writing is an activity that cannot be avoided by all students, because all learning will certainly require students to be able to write well and correctly. In this case, we need an appropriate writing learning plan with effective learning strategies, so that students understand understanding in writing skills, one of which is by writing procedural texts.

Procedure text is a text that contains a series of steps or actions to do something. In understanding procedural texts, students are required to understand in advance what things are to be prepared before doing the work. Through procedural text learning, students know what to do before carrying out something they want to do.

The learning model using powtoon media is a learning approach that can provide entertainment for students to quickly absorb material according to their abilities and interests in completing their tasks. The problems presented are adjusted to the expected response and with sufficient time allocation, so that students have time to understand the material and evaluate their potential in a fresh and entertained brain state.

This can be proven in the results of the study, where the average score of students' ability to write procedural texts was higher at 83.62 while the pre-test had an average of 63.81. In other words, it can be stated that learning to write procedural texts by using powtoon media is able to carry out various pretest and posttest data activities, namely normality test, homogeneity test, and hypothesis testing, the result is that the hypothesis H_a is accepted. From the results of the normality test, it is known that the pretest data L_{count} is 0.1444 using $\alpha = 0.05$, and N

$$= 32. \text{ Thus, } L_{count} < L_{table} \text{ is } 0.1444$$

< 0.1568 and this proves that the pretest data is normally distributed. While the posttest data is known to have L_{count} of 0.1556 < 0.1568 and this proves that the posttest data is normally distributed.

From the results of the homogeneity test, $F_{count} = 3.40$ with dk in the numerator and denominator 32 from the distribution table F for $\alpha = 0.05$, F_{table} for dk in the numerator and denominator is $F_{table} = 4.17$. So $F_{count} < F_{table}$ which is $3.40 < 4.17$. This proves that the sample comes from a homogeneous group.

The results of the hypothesis test also show that the application of the quantum teaching learning model has a positive effect on increasing the ability to appreciate poetry by class VII students of SMP Negeri 3 Pakkat for the 2020/2021 academic year. Consulted to table t 5% significant level with $df = N - 1$

$= 32 - 1 = 31$ obtained a significant level of 5% = 2.03. Because to obtained is greater than t_{table} , namely $11.72 > 2.03$, then the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected and the alternative hypothesis (H_a) is accepted.

The results of these calculations state that there is an effect after using powtoon media on the ability to write procedural texts by grade VII students of SMP Negeri 3 Pakkat for the 2020/2021 school year. This is because after using powtoon media on the ability to write procedural texts by class VII students of SMP Negeri 2 3 Pakkat for the 2020/2021 academic year

. more fun and easy to understand. When viewed from the presentation, this learning activity is very fun. In contrast to the case before using powtoon media, students focused more on the transformation of knowledge, so that students could not digest the lesson well.

Based on the results of calculations and discussion of research results, it can be concluded that powtoon media has an effect on the ability to write procedural texts by class VII students of SMP Negeri 3 Pakkat for the 2020/2021 academic year.

CONCLUSION

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Based on the results of research data analysis and hypothesis testing about the influence of powtoon media on the ability to write procedural texts by class VII students of SMP Negeri 3 Pakkat for the 2020/2021 academic year, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. The ability of students to write procedural texts before using powtoon media by class VII students of SMP Negeri 3 Pakkat for the 2020/2021 academic year is in the poor category. This can be seen in the average score obtained by students at the time of the pre-test, which is 63.81.
2. The ability of students to write procedural texts after using powtoon media by class VII students of SMP Negeri 3 Pakkat for the 2020/2021 academic year is in the good category. This can be seen in the average value of 83.62.
3. The test results of students' ability to write procedural texts using powtoon media are better than the results of students' ability tests without using powtoon media. This can be seen in the average score obtained by students at the time of the pre-test, which is 63.81.
4. Powtoon media has been proven to have a significant (positive) effect on students' ability to write procedural texts by grade VII students of SMP Negeri 3 Pakkat for the 2020/2021 academic year. This is proven by the results of the "t" test on hypothesis testing. The results of the "t" test indicate that the tcount obtained is greater than ttable, namely $11.72 > 2.03$.

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